

A STUDY OF ASCORBIC ACID SYNTHESIS BY ANIMALS *IN VIVO*

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An intraperitoneal injection of sodium pyruvate was found to induce an increased formation of ascorbic acid *in vivo* in chloretone-fed and ether-anaesthetized rats. Guinea-pigs and rabbits on the contrary are unable to synthesise ascorbic acid under similar experimental conditions.

Recently Smythe and King (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1942, 142, 529) have described *in vitro* synthesis of ascorbic acid by the tissues of chloretone-fed rats. The tissue slices from chloretone-treated rats were suspended in Ringer-bicarbonate solution in a Warburg manometer and the transformation was effected anaerobically in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂ and 95% N₂. The liver and kidney tissues of the chloretone-fed rats showed greatest evidence of ascorbic acid synthesis when a mixture of pyruvate, *dl*-glyceryl aldehyde and hexose diphosphate was employed as a substrate in the above experiment.

The above transformation was neither possible in presence of air (oxygen) nor by the tissues of normal (untreated) rats.

Thus the experimental observation of Smythe and King (*loc. cit.*) showed the possibility of ascorbic acid formation by narcotized tissues by the interaction of normal breakdown products of carbohydrate metabolism. No explanation of the mechanism of the above transformation has been put forward. In the present investigation experiments have been described to find if any simple carbohydrate moiety, especially glucose, lactate and pyruvate, can induce increased formation of ascorbic acid *in vivo* in intact rats under similar narcotized conditions.

A quick method for the determination of ascorbic acid formed in the urine of intact animals has been adopted analogous to that described by Smith and Orten (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 128, 101) for the determination of the rate of citric acid formation.

The discharge of urine from the bladder of the experimental animal was prevented by closure of the external orifice with a ligature and the ascorbic acid content of the accumulated urine was estimated titrimetrically. The ascorbic acid contents of the liver and kidney tissues of the experimental animals were also determined. Guinea-pigs and rabbits were likewise treated for comparative study.

EXPERIMENTAL

Normal rats.—Male rats of about 200 g. in weight were selected for the present investigation. These rats were bred in this laboratory and were kept on normal diet of whole wheat, brown bread, milk and water *ad libitum*.

Chloretone-fed rats.—Each of the selected rats was fed with 20 mg. of chloretone, dissolved in 0.1 c.c. of coconut oil for a period of four days. On the fourth day after feeding chloretone, the chloretone-fed rat was treated as described under experimental procedure.

Ether-anaesthetized rats.—Ether produced an increase in the concentration of ascorbic acid in the blood and tissues of rats (Ghosh, *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.* 1943, 3, 15). Normal rats after being injected intraperitoneally with test solution were allowed to inhale ether (soaked in cotton wool) inside an inverted glass funnel (12-14" diam.). Ether was poured in at intervals continuously for 2 hours and after that period the animals were suffocated to death by excessive inhalation of ether.

Guineapigs.—Male guineapigs weighing between 250 and 300 g. were selected. Experimental period was 2 hours. An intraperitoneal injection of 10 c.c. (200 mg.) of test solution was administered. Guineapigs were similarly fed for 4 consecutive days with 50 mg. of chlore-tone dissolved in 0.2 c.c. of coconut oil.

Rabbits.—Male rabbits weighing between 1 kg. and 1.5 kg. were similarly fed for 4 consecutive days with 1.0 c.c. of coconut oil containing 200 mg. of chlore-tone. 30 C.c. of saline were injected and the experimental period was for three hours.

Procedure.—Before intraperitoneal injections of the test solution were given, the external urethral orifice of each experimental animal was closed by a ligature (twine cord was found quite suitable) so that the discharge of urine from the bladder was not possible. The experimental period for rats and guineapigs was 2 hours while for rabbits it was 3 hours. At the end of the experimental period (*i.e.* 2 hours in case of rats) each animal was killed by a blow (except in case of ether anaesthesia). The animal was then fixed on a paraffin tray and a mid-line incision was made and the urinary bladder was isolated. The ureter and urethra were closed by a ligature and the bladder full of urine was carefully removed. The ligatured bladder was very cautiously washed with distilled water by gentle blowing of water from a wash-bottle. The urine inside the bladder was quantitatively collected into a small beaker (50 c.c.) containing 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid, which was used to prevent ascorbic acid oxidation. The inside of the bladder was washed thoroughly for 3-4 times ; the washings were collected along with the acidified urine and the total collection was made up to a definite volume (25 c.c.). The ascorbic acid content of the urine was determined by titration against standard 2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol solution.

The ascorbic acid contents of the liver and the kidney tissues of the experimental animals were also determined titrimetrically.

Test solutions.—A sterile physiological saline (0.9% sodium chloride autoclaved for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour under 15 lbs. pressure) solution was employed throughout the experiment.

Pyruvate, lactate and glucose (100 mg. each) were dissolved separately in 5 c.c. of the above sterile solution and were injected intraperitoneally in the experimental rats.

Results of intraperitoneal injection of saline, glucose, lactate and pyruvate into intact rats under normal, chlore-tonized and etherized conditions are given below in Table I. The results are based on the average of 6 separate sets of experiments. Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid formed in the urine which was collected from the bladder of experimental rats.

TABLE I

Mg. of ascorbic acid present in the total quantity of urine collected during 2 hours of experiment.

No.	Experimental condition of rats	Test solutions injected (5 c.c.).			
		Saline.	Glucosee (100 mg.).	Lactate (100 mg.).	Pyruvate (100 mg.).
1.	Normal (controls)	0.168	0.169	0.135	0.186
2.	Chloretone-fed	0.289	0.312	0.232	0.410
3.	Ether-anaesthetized	0.154	0.171	0.205	0.232

It is evident that chloretone is effective in inducing an increased formation of ascorbic acid in the rat. A further accelerating effect may be noticed, if pyruvate was injected intraperitoneally in the chloretone-fed rats. Pyruvate was also found to be effective in increasing the formation of ascorbic acid in intact rats under ether anaesthesia. Therefore, an inference may be drawn that the pyruvate is a major metabolite which accumulates and simultaneously undergoes transformation into ascorbic acid under the action of both chloretone and ether. Accumulation of pyruvic acid and the mechanism of its transformation into ascorbic acid still remains to be proved experimentally. However, the present observation indicates that pyruvic acid takes a leading role in the above transformation.

The ascorbic acid content of the liver and kidney tissues of the normal, chloretone-fed and etherised rats under various experimental conditions are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Mg. of ascorbic acid per g. of (moist) tissue. Experimental period was 2 hours. Number of rats for each set of experiment was 6.

No.	Expt. condition	Test solution injected							
		(a) Liver				(b) Kidney			
		Saline	Glucose	Lactate	Pyruvate	Saline.	Glucose.	Lactate.	Pyruvate.
1.	Normal rates	0.185	0.162	0.118	0.166	0.164	0.160	0.127	0.110
2.	Chloretone-fed rats	0.279	0.217	0.191	0.226	0.231	0.256	0.220	0.226
3.	Etherised rats	0.217	0.242	0.260	0.232				

From Table II it will be observed that the ascorbic acid concentration in the liver and kidney tissues was greater in chloretone-treated and ether-anaesthetized rats than those of untreated rats under identical experimental conditions. The total amount of ascorbic acid in these organs, however, was found to have decreased when injected with sodium pyruvate and sodium lactate. This decrease in the ascorbic acid content is probably due to introduction of an excess concentration of sodium ion.

The output of ascorbic acid in the urine of guineapigs under the conditions of normal, chloretone-fed, ether-anaesthesia and auoxia are given in Table III for the sake of comparative study. 200 Mg. of pyruvate in 10 c.c. of saline were injected

into normal and chloretone-fed guineapigs. Only very slight increase in the ascorbic acid content in the urine of chloretone-fed guineapigs was observed. No marked effect of pyruvate was, however, observed in the case of chloretone-fed guineapigs. It is therefore clear that ascorbic acid synthesis is not possible by guineapigs under narcotized condition.

TABLE III

Mg. of ascorbic acid present in the urine of guineapigs under experimental conditions noted.				
(a) 10 c.c. of saline injected.				
A	Normal	Chloredone-fed	Ether anaesthetized	Anoxia
	0.076	0.093	0.059	0.036
(b) 10 c.c. of pyruvate (100 mg. in saline) solution.				
B	Normal	Chloretone-fed		
	0.062	0.072		

Similar treatment with chloretone and saline injection produced no increased elimination of ascorbic acid in the urine of rabbits (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Each rabbit was fed with 200 mg. of chloretone for a period of 4 days. 100 c.c. of saline were injected intraperitoneally. Experimental period was 2 hours.

Mg. of ascorbic acid collected from the bladder.		
No.	Normal rabbit.	Chloretone-fed rabbit.
1.	0.433	0.325
2.	0.274	0.260
	Mean 0.353	0.292

C O N C L U S I O N

Rats can excrete an increased quantity of ascorbic acid when fed with chloretone. Still more marked increase in the ascorbic acid content of the urine of chloretone-fed rats and of the urine of ether-anaesthetized rats was observed when injected with 100 mg. of pyruvate intraperitoneally. It seems likely that the pyruvate (pyruvic acid) may be an important metabolite or precursor which is concerned in ascorbic acid synthesis by the rat under narcotized condition.

The ascorbic acid content of the tissues like liver and kidney of the rat was found to be higher under narcotized condition. It is likely that all the organs and tissues of the rat under the action of narcotics take part in the synthesis of ascorbic acid. Similar views have been expressed by Sutton, Kaeser and Hansard (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1942, 144, 183). It would thus appear that no particular tissue or organ of the rat is responsible for ascorbic acid synthesis.

Guineapigs and rabbits are unable to synthesise ascorbic acid under similar narcotized conditions.

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